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Deep Learning based Long Short-Term Memory Recurrent Neural Network for Stock Price Movement Prediction

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Abstract

Background/Objectives: Stock price movement prediction is a difficult task that is simulated using machine learning algorithms to anticipate stock returns.

Methods: This study uses the Long-Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Recurrent Neural Network deep learning algorithm combined with the stock's price action method to predict the movement of intraday price for short-term forecasting. The dataset uses data points such as date, open, high, low, close, volume. The predictions of price movement accuracy were tested on State Bank of India (SBI) stock and one year of the trading dataset used for training the algorithm.

Findings: The proposed algorithm gives the prediction of price movement accuracy is up to 98.9%, MSE is 0.918 and MAPE 0.987 with one year of the training dataset. The SBI share price can be predicted one day before and the price prediction can be range level, which means upward or downward. The proposed method has proven to be better than traditional machine learning methods in terms of prediction accuracy and speed. **Novelty:** This research suggested a fine-tuned and personalized deep learning prediction system that coupled the price action technique with LSTM to make predictions. The combination of the price action method with deep learning algorithm in forecasting is not tried before but this paper does.

Keywords: LongShortTerm Memory; Stock Trading; Stock Price prediction; Recurrent Neural Network; Deep Learning; Machine Learning 1

1 Introduction

Investing in stock market is always been difficult. It takes more science than fluke to pick the right company at the appropriate time to invest in. Various machine learning

approaches have been utilized in stock market prediction over the years, but deep learning models are increasingly being used because of the increased amount of data and the anticipation of more accurate predictions⁽¹⁾. Deep learning uses a variety of techniques and algorithms, one of which is a type of neural network called the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN)⁽²⁾. The ensemble of time series analysis with the price action method is a rare phenomenon of predicting the stock price in a day trading. The proposed method takes those two attributes as an input to RNN and forecasts the value. Linear regression and ARIMA (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average) [x3] is the techniques to predict the values up to 97.25 but the researchers tested around 100 days only but the proposed RNN based LSTM can give up to 98.9% accuracy in price movement according to 365 days of testing. With the one-year time frame MSE (Mean Squared Error) and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) can be better than ARIMA and SVM (Support Vector Machine) methods.

In⁽³⁾, Sirignano and Cont introduced a deep learning approach that was trained on a universal collection of financial market features. The dataset comprised all bought and sold records for all trades, as well as withdrawals of orders for about thousands NASDAQ equities via the stock exchange's order book. The NN is made up of three layers: LSTM units, a feed-forward layer, and finally, a feed-forward layer using rectified linear units (ReLUs), with the Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) algorithm as an optimizer. Those universal model could generalize and cover stocks that weren't part of the training set. Despite mentioning the benefits of a universal paradigm, the training costs were remained high. Meanwhile, it's unknown whether there are any meaningless features tainted when feeding data into the model due to the deep learning algorithm's inexplicit programming. The authors discovered that performing feature selection previously training the model would have been better and that it was an efficient technique to reduce computational complexity.

In⁽⁴⁾, Fischer and Krauss used LSTM to predict monetary markets. The dataset they used was Thomson Reuters' S&P 500 index constituents. The research drawback is a lack of background knowledge in the financial domain. The effort to train an LSTM with long-time dependencies was not mentioned by the author.

The research⁽⁵⁾ used RNN and LSTM to forecast the price of cryptocurrencies, with the feature engineering part improved using the Boruta method, and it performs almost same to the random forest classifier. They employed Bayesian optimization to select Long Short Term Memory attributes in addition to feature selection. Overfitting is the main issue in this study. The problem of anticipating Bitcoin price trends is comparable to that of predicting stock market prices. This work is vulnerable by hidden features and noise buried in the price data.

Hushani⁽⁶⁾ compared four stock market price movement prediction strategies, including an ARIMA, Vector Auto Regression (VAR), Long Short Term Memory, and Nonlinear Auto-Regression with exogenous inputs, in a recent study (NARX). The NASDAQ closing price was utilised as the basis for the analysis. The findings demonstrated that NARX made accurate short-term predictions but failed to make long-term predictions. Long-term dependencies can be learned by LSTM networks, giving them a watchful influence on time series prediction. The authors of⁽⁷⁾ used a dynamic LSTM network to forecast Nifty prices using open, close, low and high as features, and got an RMSE of 0.00859 in terms of daily percentage changes.

Yang Li⁽⁸⁾ introduced a novel method to forecast trading stock movement with deep learning, Gated Recurrent Unit Network and set of RNN. This combined architecture produces the accuracy of price movement by 33.34% and it improves the rate of precision is upto 40%. The research uses trading dataset acquired from S&P 500. There are two stages to the blending ensemble model. Two RNN, one LSTM, and one GRU make up the first level, which is followed by a fully connected NN as the second level. The time series events in the input data are effectively captured by RNNs, LSTMs, and GRU models, and the fully connected NN is utilized to joint numerous individual prediction outputs to improve forecasting precision.

This paper is organized as follows: introductions about the proposed model and detailed literature study are carried out in section 1. The methodology of the proposed study is discussed in section 3. Section 4 will be a detailed discussion on experimental results and the conclusion and future work of this study are provided in section 5.

2 Methodology

The proposed architecture used open, close, high and low price levels and volumes to apply LSTM RNN algorithm to predict price movements for the next trading day. Instead of modelling the data to time series, and decided to use one day ahead indices data to predict the price trend of the next day to develop an efficient prediction model. The data set can be imported from the National Stock Exchange (NSE) website through nsepy library for training. TensorFlow and nsepy libraries have used in this proposed model. The backend for the LSTM model will be TensorFlow, and the historical stock data will be retrieved using nsepy. The Figure 1 explores the overall process of proposed system.

The imported libraries can be processed by the RNN algorithm. The algorithm can be trained by i_t , \tilde{C}_t , f_t , ct , o_t , ht . The formulae for computing each of these entities are as follows, based on the RNN architecture (Figure 2).

$$i_t = \sigma(W_{ix}X_t + W_{ih}h_{t-1} + b_i) \quad (1)$$

Fig 1. Proposed methodology by using LSTM

$$\tilde{C}_t = \sigma(W_{cx}x_t + W_{ch}h_{t-1} + b_c) \tag{2}$$

$$f_t = \sigma(W_{fx}x_t + W_{fh}h_{t-1} + b_f) \tag{3}$$

$$c_t = f_t c_{t-1} + i_t \tilde{C}_t \tag{4}$$

$$o_t = \sigma(W_{ox}x_t + W_{oh}h_{t-1} + b_o) \tag{5}$$

$$h_t = o_t \tanh(c_t) \tag{6}$$

The historical SBI stock dataset can then be extracted from the nsepy library and processed using the approach that involves successively obtaining sets of training dataset, with each batch having a size of [batch size, 1]. Then there will be a measured output batch for each set of input data. If num_unrollings=3 and batch size=4, for example, a collection of unrolled batches would look like this:

Input data: [x0,x10,x20,x30], [x1,x11,x21,x31], [x2,x12,x22,x32] [x0,x10,x20,x30], [x1,x11,x21,x31], [x2,x12,x22,x32]

Output data: [x1,x11,x21,x31], [x2,x12,x22,x32], [x3,x13,x23,x33] [x1,x11,x21,x31], [x2,x12,x22,x32], [x3,x13,x23,x33]

2.1 Periotic Data Acquisition

You will also not make the output for x_t to x_{t+1} to make your model more robust. always x_{t+1} to x_{t+1} . Instead, you'll take a random sample from the set $\{x_{t+1}, x_{t+2}, \dots, x_{t+N}, x_{t+1}, x_{t+2}, \dots, x_{t+N}\}$ where NN is a small window size. In this case, you're assuming the following:

Fig 2. Data flow with RNN

Fig 3. Data Augmentation

$x_{t+1}, x_{t+2}, \dots, x_{t+N}$ they will be close to each other. Below is a graphic representation of how a batch of data is created. Move each cursor by one to acquire the next batch of data. (Figure 3).

The proposed method developed and tested through python and windows 10 operating system. The sample coding of the system is given below (Figure 4). SBI stock data can be tested and visualized.

The above code can apply to the dataset which taken in the year 2021. Table 1 and Table 2 is the sample data which import from the NSE website.

3 Result and Discussions

According to the algorithms and experimental result, the suggested method has a prediction accuracy of 98.9 percent, which is better than previous models. The prediction accuracy of LSTM with RNN is the most fruitful and compared with ARIMA it has differences of almost 2%. The forecast shows the price movement for the next day with two statuses, indicating whether it will be upward or downward (Figure 5). If the price movement is downward, the stock price will be negative the next day; otherwise, the stock price will be positive.

```

main.py +
1 testdataframe= gh(symbol='SBIIN',start=dt.datetime(2021,1,1),end=dt.datetime(2021,9,18))
2 testdataframe['Date'] = testdataframe.index
3 testdata = pd.DataFrame(columns = ['Date', 'Open', 'High', 'Low', 'Close'])
4 testdata['Date'] = testdataframe['Date']
5 testdata['Open'] = testdataframe['Open']
6 testdata['High'] = testdataframe['High']
7 testdata['Low'] = testdataframe['Low']
8 testdata['Close'] = testdataframe['Close']
9 real_stock_price = testdata.iloc[:, 1:2].values
10 dataset_total = pd.concat((data2['Open'], testdata['Open']), axis = 0)
11 inputs = dataset_total[len(dataset_total) - len(testdata) - 60:].values
12 inputs = inputs.reshape(-1,1)
13 inputs = sc.transform(inputs)
    
```

Fig 4. Screenshot of sample code

Table 1. Daily data of SBI stock

Date	Open	High	Low	Close	Volume
Oct 29, 2021	501.50	512.65	488.40	502.15	31,355,893
Oct 28, 2021	519.60	520.55	497.60	501.35	28,140,401
Oct 27, 2021	513.70	526.85	512.75	519.15	29,463,032
Oct 26, 2021	507.60	518.20	507.60	512.55	21,107,457
Oct 25, 2021	506.50	515.45	497.85	506.50	35,619,415
Oct 22, 2021	504.60	508.70	500.00	502.95	24,080,485
Oct 21, 2021	504.90	506.50	491.75	502.95	20,808,243
Oct 20, 2021	488.80	507.50	483.10	499.90	34,080,545
Oct 19, 2021	500.35	504.20	483.25	488.20	20,645,100
Oct 18, 2021	494.00	501.00	491.70	497.95	20,084,248
Oct 14, 2021	482.00	493.90	482.00	490.60	23,431,826
Oct 13, 2021	486.15	486.15	478.00	481.70	17,638,983
Oct 12, 2021	470.00	484.40	468.10	483.00	33,763,609
Oct 11, 2021	460.00	474.95	458.65	469.25	20,686,981
Oct 08, 2021	461.90	464.00	454.25	458.00	16,521,128
Oct 07, 2021	462.10	464.00	457.10	457.90	9,984,651
Oct 06, 2021	465.00	471.00	453.65	457.20	19,056,690
Oct 05, 2021	462.00	469.00	458.70	464.70	16,487,568
Oct 04, 2021	453.80	464.40	451.60	463.15	16,246,765
Oct 01, 2021	448.50	455.55	443.80	451.65	14,777,309

Table 2. Monthly data of SBI stock

Date	Open	High	Low	Close	Volume
Dec 01, 2021	464.45	500.45	463.80	481.15	166,429,616
Nov 01, 2021	508.50	542.30	454.30	460.55	482,271,634
Oct 01, 2021	448.50	526.85	443.80	502.15	453,980,329
Sep 01, 2021	427.50	471.90	425.10	453.00	408,763,525
Aug 01, 2021	434.75	467.45	401.25	426.05	619,336,083
Jul 01, 2021	420.30	444.40	417.15	431.80	365,053,983
Jun 01, 2021	426.05	441.95	400.50	419.20	650,335,327
May 01, 2021	349.60	433.65	341.40	424.35	1,295,320,532
Apr 01, 2021	367.70	371.90	321.30	353.50	929,066,645
Mar 01, 2021	395.10	408.90	345.20	364.30	849,338,663
Feb 01, 2021	285.10	427.70	282.75	390.15	1,532,347,646
Jan 01, 2021	274.90	310.90	269.50	282.10	777,947,672

Fig 5. SBI stock price prediction

Table 3. Comparison of prediction methods

Models	MSE	MAPE	Accuracy
ARIMA	1.681	1.187	97.259 %
Linear Regression	3.967	2.012	92.364 %
SVM	3.121	1.719	97.862 %
LSTM-RNN	0.918	0.987	98.957 %

shows the clear picture that LSTM with RNN predicts better accuracy than ARIMA (97.2), Linear regression (92.3), SVM (97.862). The MSE of the LSTM is 0.98 which is closer to zero compared to ARIMA, Linear regression and SVM models which has 1.6, 3.9 and 3.2 respectively. Likewise, the MAPE of the proposed system is better than the existing researches that are 0.98, and the MAPE of ARIMA, Linear regression, and SVM are 1.187, 2.012, and 1.719 respectively (Figure 6 a-c).

Fig 6. (a) Comparison of MSE (b) Comparison of MAPE (c) Comparison of Accuracy

The error rate is very minimum that could be very important when the prediction of real-time share prices. The differences in the MSE and MAPE of existing methods from the proposed method are 2.0 and 1.1 respectively. As per the result, the time series analysis with RNN and LSTM produced much better than the existing time series analysis.

4 Conclusion and Future Work

This research suggests RNN based LSTM was developed to anticipate future prices for SBI stock the results of the tests show that 98.9 percent prediction accuracy compared to ARIMA and Linear regression-based models and even produced better movement signal than the indicators such as RSI, Bollinger band, and Moving Average. The research used SBI stock historical data taken from NSE (National Stock Exchange) for the past one year (from 1st January to 31st December 2021) to forecast the price movement, particularly the model can track the evolution of opening prices for SBI stock with the addition of movement signal. In the future, the optimum sets of data length and training epochs can be used to enhance the accuracy of intra-day with time frame forecast.

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